

WELCOME TO THE AI-PRISM SMART JOURNEY! NEWSLETTER #1

Let's go !

Dear {{ contact.FIRSTNAME }},

The **#AIPRISM25** team gives you a warm welcome to this **newsletter #1**. Almost eight months ago, we started our project, and since then, many news, events and technical advancements have happened.

As part of the AI-PRISM Smart journey, you have access to this compilation of activities that are significantly AI-powering, human-centred robot interactions for smart manufacturing.

[Learn more about AI-PRISM!](#)

MEETING OUR PROJECT COORDINATOR

Ana Gonzalez Segura (NTT Data Spain) is our Project Coordinator. She is at the frontline of AI-PRISM, ensuring that all 25 organisations participate, innovate, collaborate, and accomplish a common objective: turning the manufacturing industry and its SMEs into smart through digitalisation.

[Meet her!](#)

INTRODUCING OUR TECHNICAL MANAGER

Francisco Fraile (Polytechnical University of Valencia) is our Technical Manager. He is leading the Technical board of the project, making certain that everyone is heard and provides technical insights

Let's meet!
Francisco Fraile
AI-PRISM Technical Manager
What is his reflection on AI-PRISM?
Find it out!

Funded by the European Union

based on their expertise.

[Meet him!](#)

TECHNICAL ADVANCEMENTS

The #AI-PRISM25 is a strong and interdisciplinary team comprising the Smart manufacturing value chain and specifically strategic domains:

- ✓ Collaboration environment
- ✓ Robot perception & cognition
- ✓ Robot programming & Human factors.

Throughout these months, every team member has been working on tasks involving our demonstrators and the project's architecture.

DELIVERABLES

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DELIVERABLES D1.1
Technology Benchmarking & Project Vision

TECHNOLOGY BENCHMARKING & PROJECT VISION

The deliverable presents technologies and the first standards that laid the foundations for developing our project.

[Read more](#)

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DELIVERABLES D5.1
Task Analysis for Benchmarking and Design Requirements (I)

TASK ANALYSIS FOR BENCHMARKING & DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

The methodology, results, conclusions and future work in the human factors and psychological aspects involved in each use case are part of the content of this deliverable.

[Read more](#)

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DELIVERABLES D1.2
Use cases scenarios and requirements analysis (I)

USE CASE SCENARIOS & REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

The document reports the efforts done in the scope of tasks of the AI-PRISM project towards the definition of the use cases and the requirement analysis specifications.

[Read more](#)

DEMONSTRATORS

We will test our innovations in different manufacturing sectors (furniture, electronics, built-in home appliances, beverages and discrete manufacturing) based in Spain, Poland, Greece, Turkey and Austria.

In these months, the methodology established in the proposal has been followed by our industrial partners, researchers and tech providers. It consisted of:

- ✓ Detailed descriptions of the demonstrators
- ✓ Online workshops
- ✓ Physical visits to start the data collection.

By the 8th month, we had already finished the detailed descriptions of our demonstrators, executed the four online workshops and visited all our use cases.

ANDREU WORLD - DIGITISING THE ART OF SANDING!

Our team participated in an exciting data collection experiment that combined RGBD cameras and eye-tracking technology in Valencia, Spain.

[Learn more](#)

ATHENIAN BREWERY - DIGITISING BEER BREWING!

We explored the 4 processes that will be conducted, raising questions, taking photos and videos and discussing the possibilities of human-robot collaborations.

[Discover them](#)

SILVERLINE - DIGITISING BUILT-IN APPLIANCES!

In a hybrid visit to Silverline's premises, we eye-tracked 3 processes and detected interesting findings that will make operators utilize their time wisely.

[Find them out](#)

KEBA - DISCRETE MANUFACTURING!

Our team visited KEBA's premises in Austria to collect data on 4 tasks at the PBC testing area and interview 2 operators.

[Learn more](#)

VIGO PHOTONICS - DIGITISING ELECTRONICS!

We visited VIGO premises in Poland and collected data, documenting all the experience with photos and discussing technical aspects of the pilot.

[Discover them](#)

In parallel to the technical advancements of the project, we have been active in raising awareness campaigns for topics that are of relevant concern, coinciding with international days and other initiatives.

EUROPEAN YEAR OF SKILLS - HOW ARE WE ALIGNED WITH THE INITIATIVE?

This year kick starts the European Year of Skills, an initiative that focuses on the green and digital transitions and how they are opening new opportunities for people. We joined the initiative!

[Find out more](#)

INTERNATIONAL DAY OF EDUCATION - REFLECTION BY SARAH FLETCHER

To commemorate the International Day of Education and reinforce our commitment to this universal right, our colleague Dr Sarah Fletcher, reflected on a quote by Kurt Lewin.

[Read more](#)

THE WOMEN BEHIND AI-PRISM

To commemorate International Women's Day and Women and Girls in Science Day, the #AIPRISM25 women took the floor to address the needed promotion of equality in science, technology, and innovation.

[In science](#)

[In SSH](#)

HADEA/MCID DIGITAL SYMPOSIUM

Andrei Rusu from NTT DATA Romania was invited by the European Commission and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) to provide an overview of AI-PRISM. Andrei gave a brief overview of our project, their first Horizon project, which represents a significant milestone for the entity.

[Learn more](#)

EUROPEAN ROBOTICS FORUM 2023

We participated in two workshops and a digital booth within the forum in Odense, Denmark, which has one of the world's leading robotic clusters. More than 400 visitors learned how AI-PRISM is developing a human-centred AI-based solutions ecosystem targeted to manufacturing scenarios.

[Learn more](#)

COMING UP

DIGITAL MANUFACTURING INDUSTRIAL SUMMIT 2023

From the 25th to the 27th of April, the Digital Manufacturing Industrial Summit 2023 (DMIS2023) will be in Valencia, Spain. DMIS2023 is a **free-of-charge forum** that aims to provide a networking conference to answer questions about what the industry 4.0, 5.0, and "Made in Europe" key concepts framing the European manufacturing landscape mean in practices and how they are shaping the present and the future of it.

AI-PRISM will hold a workshop and participate actively in the forum.

[Register now!](#)

AI-PRISM Horizon Europe

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